

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF HEALTH DRINK ADVERTISEMENT IN TELEVISION ON HIGH SCHOOL CHILDREN'S IN BENGALURU

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Abstract: *The purpose of this research is to make a review of the impact of Health Drink TV Advertisements on high school children in Bengaluru. In order, to boost up children's energy level, there are number of varieties of branded health drinks available in the market. The main objective of this study is to understand the High School children awareness and preference towards the different brands of Health drink. The main statistical tools that are been used are percentage and chi-square test. There are four brands of Health drinks are available in the study area that are Horlicks, Complan, Bournvita and Boost. While comparing with soft drinks Health drinks are safer, which are effective for those below 20. Since Television Advertisement has become a part of regular TV broadcast and viewers of these advertisement message can influence to buy the product. The study used 50 respondents for the purpose to get feedback on favourite brand of health drinks among high school children. The study report that most of the children preferred the brand Horlicks, and taste, attractive offers/ free gifts are the main factor for purchasing the specific Health Drink*

Keywords: Advertisement, Awareness, Brand image, Behaviour of children, Health Drinks

Introduction

The Television Advertisement on Health Drinks nowadays impacts children more. As when children watch TV Advertisement, they get more awareness about their branded Health Drink. TV Advertisement targets children and they present their advertisement in a such a way where the children get attracted towards the brand. As Horlicks initially targets at growing children because children need adequate and balanced nutrition. Both Complan and Horlicks are available in different flavours in different package size. The study used 50 respondents for the purpose to get feedback on favourite brand of health drinks among high school children. 50 per cent of respondents prefer Horlicks, 40 per cent of respondents prefer Boost, 4 per cent of respondents prefer Complan, 6 per cent of respondents prefer Bournvita. Horlicks is one-half top-rated health drink in India. Now Horlicks has more flavours including vanilla, toffee, etc. 46 percentage of respondents choose taste as a main factor that motivates them to buy

particular health drink. The study aim is to find the most preferred health drink brand among High School children. There may be various factors influencing them to buy Health Drink on advertisement, packaging, attractive offers, free gifts, and taste. The study wants to know what feature thus children's like in TV Advertisement on awareness about their product. Both Horlicks and Complan are involved in large amount of advertising in print and television over decades. As both brands have more success in the market and this study aims in disclosing the impact of Health drink TV Advertisement on High School children.

Statement of Problem

Nowadays, many manufacturing companies produce health drinks which play an important role in satisfying the needs of the young children. There are companies who established a name in the field of business have emerged as manufacturing new brands of health drinks. Number of health drinks such as Horlicks, Boost, Complan, Bournvita etc. are there. The young children need and preference are changing as per the current market scenario. The children get attracted towards the free gifts, taste and package of branded health drink. The large amount of money spent on Advertisement make the young children be aware of their latest brands in the market. In this study the researcher is interested in understanding the study on brand awareness and to know what motives them to buy a particular brand of health drinks. We witness that children's preference varies from brand to brand on basis of taste, price, gifts, smell, age etc.

Importance of the study

This is an analyses on High school children preference towards health drinks in Bengaluru. An attempt has been made by the researcher to know the consumer preference, awareness regarding brand, price, quality, advertisement, and satisfaction etc., The findings of the study will ultimately reveal why certain brands are preferred by children.

Objective of the study

The study aims at

- To know the favourite brand and preferable features of Health Drink among High school children.
- To find the awareness created by TV Advertisement about Health drink.

Research Methodology

This study has made on High School children preference to Health drinks in Bengaluru. The questionnaire includes questions related to socio-economic profile of high school children and their details of their favourite brand, the features motivate them to buy, what awareness they gained through TV advertisement on health drinks. To analyse on High school children's preferences on the Health Drinks, primary data was collected from 50 respondents through questionnaire. The main statistical tools that are been used are percentage and chi-square test. A well-set questionnaire was prepared for the purpose of collecting data. A set of questionnaire includes all individual respondents personnel background information of the high school children on preference features of health drink, to know the favourite brand of health drink and awareness created by Television Advertisement about Health drink.

Limitation of the Study

This study is limited to Bengaluru only. There are many more health drinks available in the market, apart from that only 5 famous health drinks are selected for the study.

Findings and Results

Socio- economic characteristics may influence the brand sticking tendency of Health drinks users. In order to find the relationship between socio- economic characteristics and brand sticking tendency of Health drinks, the following statistical analysis has been made on the basis of null hypothesis.

Null hypothesis: there is no significant relation between the socio- economic characteristics and favourite brand.

This null hypothesis has been statistically tested with the help of chi- square test at 5% level of significance.

Favourite brand of Health Drink

Favourite brand of High School children on the basis of Age

Some features of brand may attract a particular age group children and few may not attract other age group children. The relationship between age and favourite brand of High School children has been studied. Table 1 shows the relationship between age and favourite brand of High School children.

Table 1: Favourite brand of Health Drink

S:No	Brand	Age group		Total
		13-14	14-15	
1	Horlicks	10	16	26
2	Boost	11	9	20
3	Complan	2	1	3
4	Bournvita	1	-	1
5	Total	24	26	50

$\chi^2 = 4.614$ degree of freedom= 3 Table value = 7.815

The chi square test was used to find favourite brand of high school children depends on Age, so the calculated value of χ^2 is less than the Table value. The relationship between age and favourite brand of High School children is insignificant. Hence it can be concluded that null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between age and favourite brand of High school children.

Favourite brand of High School children on the basis of gender

Male and female are having different taste and nature. So, the favourite brand of High school children may differ according to their gender. In this Table, we will study the relationship on favourite brand of High school children on the basis of gender. Table 2 and Chart 2 shows the relation on favourite brand of high school children on the basis of gender.

Table 2: Favourite brand of High School Children on the basis of Gender

S.no	Brand	Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
1	Horlicks	10	16	26

2	Boost	7	13	20
3	Complan	2	1	3
4	Bournvita	1	-	1
5	Total	20	30	50

$\chi^2 = 2.6229$ Degree of freedom = 3 table value = 7.815

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the Table value. The relationship between gender and the favourite brand of High school children is insignificant. Hence it can be concluded that the null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between gender and brand preference. Some features of a brand may attract High school children and few children change their brand due to taste, colour, flavour and offers. Table 3 shows that maximum of respondents opted for Horlicks brand. Hence it can be concluded that respondents prefer Horlicks brand.

Awareness created by TV Advertisement about Health Drink

The Table 4 shows that, 92 percentage of respondents are aware about their brand by TV Advertisement. The TV Advertisement is powerful media that creates awareness about the product, but 8 percent of respondents are not aware about their brand by TV Advertisement.

Table 4: Awareness created by TV Advertisement about Health Drink

Option	No of respondents	Percentage
Awareness created	46	92
Awareness not created	4	8
Total	50	100

Sources: primary data

Table 4 shows that, 92 percentage of respondents agree that they are aware of their brand by seeing TV Advertisement. Other 8 percentage of respondents were not aware of their brand by TV advertisement. Awareness created by TV Advertisement about Health drink has been reached to 92 percentage of respondents.

Purpose of buying particular brand

The Table 5, study on purpose of buying particular brand by High school children. The Table 5 reveals that 46 percentage of respondents like taste so, maximum of them buy the product due to the taste. 8 percentage of respondents like smell that motivates them to buy that particular brand.

Table 5: Purpose of buying particular brand

Factors	No. of respondents	Percentage
Taste	23	46
Attractive offers	12	24
Smell	4	8
Nutrition	11	22
Total	50	100

Source: primary data

The Table 5 shows that, 46 percentage of respondents like taste in their particular brand, 24 percentage of respondents like attractive offers in their particular brand, 8 percentage of respondents like smell in their favourite brand, 22 percent of respondents prefer nutrition in their brand. Hence it can be concluded that the purpose of buying particular brand on basis of taste.

Number of years of Health Drink been consumed

The number of years of health Drink been consumed by respondents are discussed in Table 6. It is observed that 38 percentage of respondents consume Health Drink in 5-10 years and 14 percentage of respondents consume health drink more than 10 years.

Table 6: Number of years of Health Drink been consumed

No. of years	No of respondents	Percentage
Up to 2 years	10	20
2-5	14	28
5-10	19	38
More than 10	7	14
Total	50	100

Source: primary data

The Table 6 shows that, 20 percentage of respondents have been using the health drink up to 2 years, 28 percentage of respondents have been using the health drink for 2- 5 years, 38 percentage of respondents have been using the health drink for 5- 10 years, 14 percentage of respondents have been using the health drink for more than 10 years.

What feature attracts you to buy Health Drink

Table 7 studies on feature attracts to buy the health drink. It is observed that 44 percentage of respondents like taste that motivates them to buy health drink and very less of them like

package of the product that attracts them to buy the health drink. So, there are many features that attracts high school children to buy the nutritious drink.

Table 7: What feature attracts you to buy Health drink

Features	No of respondents	Percentage
Package	4	8
Free gifts	19	38
Taste	22	44
Colour	5	10
Total	50	100

Source: primary data

The Table 7 shows that, 8 percentage of respondents like features in package of health drink, 38 percentage of respondents like features of free gifts in health drink, 44 percentage of respondents like taste in the health drink, 10 percentage of respondents like colour of health drinks.

Classification of respondents on shifting of Brand

The reasons behind shifting of brand by respondents are discussed in Table 8. It has been observed that 32 percentage of respondents shift to other brands on basis of attractive offers and 16 percentage of respondents shift brand on basis of packaging. 24 percentage of respondents have other reason to shift to another brand.

Table 8: Classification of Respondents on shifting of brand

Option	No of respondents	Percentage
Packaging	8	16
Taste	14	28
Attractive offers	16	32
Other	12	24
Total	8	100

Source: primary data

Table 8 shows that, 16 percentage of respondents change their brand on basis of packaging, 28 percentage of respondents change their brand on basis of taste, 32 percentage of respondents change their brand on basis on attractive offers, 24 percentage of respondents change their brand for other reasons.

Table 9: Influence of TV Advertisement on selection of Health Drink

Option	No of respondents	Percentage
Influenced	46	92
Not Influenced	4	8
Total	50	100

Source: primary data

The Table 9 shows that, 92 percentage of the respondents report that TV Advertisement influence them to buy Health Drink, rest 8 percentage of the respondents report that TV Advertisement does not influence them to opt for Healthy drink. Hence it has been concluded that 92 percentage of respondents are influenced by TV Advertisement.

Factors which motivates the children to buy Health Drink

Table 10 shows the factors in TV Advertisement that motivate the children to buy health drink. It has been observed that 32 percentage of respondents are motivated by the message

given in the Advertisement.

Table 10: Factors which motivates the children to buy Health Drink

Factors	No of respondents	Percentage
Celebrities	15	30
Message given in the advertisement	16	32
Attractive	7	14
Sound and music	8	16
Sceneries	4	8
Total	50	100

Source: primary data

Table 10 shows that, 30 percentage of respondents buy the health drink as they are motivated by the celebrities, 32 percentage of respondents are motivated to buy the health drink by seeing message given in the advertisement, 14 percentage of respondents like the attractiveness in the product which motivates them to buy the product, 16 percentage of respondents like sound and music of the product in TV Advertisement, 8 percentage of respondents like sceneries created by TV Advertisement in health drink.

Most attractive feature of TV Advertisement

The Table 11 shows that, 38 percentage of respondents like the awareness about the product in TV Advertisement and very few respondents like sound and music in Television Advertisement.

Table 11: Most attractive feature of TV Advertisement

Feature	No of respondents	Percentage
Visibility	10	20
Sound and music	8	16
Presentation	13	26
Awareness about the product	19	38
Total	50	100

Source: primary data

Table 11 shows that, 20 percentage of respondents liked factors of visibility in TV Advertisement, 16 percentage of respondents like sound and music in TV Advertisement, 26 percentage of respondents like factors of presentation of the product in TV Advertisement, 38 percentage of respondents like awareness about the product in TV Advertisement. so, most of the High School children like the awareness created about the product in TV advertisement.

Table 12: Information given by TV Advertisement

Factors	No of respondents	Percentage
Price	4	8
Feature of product	15	30
Offers and prices	10	20
Ingredients of product	4	8
Availability of the product	5	10
Benefits of the product	12	24
Total	50	100

Source: primary data

Table 12 shows that, 8 percentage of respondents gets information on price of the product in TV Advertisement, 30 percentage of respondents gets information on feature of product, 20 percentage of respondents gets information on offers and prices, 8 percentage of respondents gets information on ingredients of product, 10 percentage of respondents gets information on availability of the product, 24 percentage of respondents gets information on benefits of the product.

Conclusion

All High School children like Health drinks and through TV advertisement, children gain more awareness about different brands of Health Drinks. Impact of TV advertisement makes them to change their brand of Health Drinks. Most of children consume Health Drink based on the taste, flavour, nutrition. From this study, it has been concluded that there are wide varieties of products available in the market to the buyers of all segments and most of the high school children prefer Horlicks. However, the Indian buyers mostly concentrate in the consumption of Horlicks which has reached every corner of the country.

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